

Code of conduct for QUAREP-LiMi

Code of conduct for QUAREP-LiMi	1
General Provisions.....	1
Mission Statement of QUAREP-LiMi	1
Commitment to Reproducibility & Integrity.....	2
Transparency & Accountability.....	2
Respectful Communication and Ethical Behavior.....	2
Constructive Feedback.....	2
Efficient Online Collaboration	2
General Expectations & Conflict Resolution	3
Authorship and Acknowledgment of Data and Internal Discussions.....	3
Reasoning.....	3
Authorship.....	3
Work Products	4
Working Group Data and Other Shared Information	4
Meeting Recordings.....	4
Overlap with Outside Work of Members	5

General Provisions

Mission Statement of QUAREP-LiMi

The Consortium for Quality Assessment and Reproducibility for Instruments and Images in Light Microscopy (QUAREP-LiMi), formed by a global community of practitioners, researchers, developers, service providers, funders, publishers, policy makers and industry representatives related to the use of light microscopy, is committed to democratizing access to quantitative and reproducible light microscopy and the data generated by it. Our mission is to provide a comprehensive set of community-agreed guidelines, protocols, automation procedures and other resources aimed at improving quality control, quality assurance, and instrument/method calibration. The stakeholders advocate for the use of the highest level of reproducibility for data generated by light microscopy methods in scientific research and biotechnology applications.

In support of achieving its mission, QUAREP-LiMi: 1) sanctions Working Groups to form teams that focus on specific technical or outreach topics; 2) maintains, disseminates, and teaches best practices, protocols, and software tools; and 3) collaborates with providers of reference materials, instrumentation or other tools that enable the easy implementation of best practices at the community-level.

To foster these aims and outcomes, members of the consortium agree to a general Code of Conduct (CoC). This CoC serves as a guideline for both ethical and behavioral conduct. This CoC references the consortium by-laws that are accessible here: [doi:10.5281/zenodo.14884070](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14884070)

Commitment to Reproducibility & Integrity

Members and other contributors strive for the highest standard of quality control and reproducibility in all microscopy work. They 1) share protocols, data, and results openly to support verification and reuse by others; 2) uphold integrity by giving credit to contributors and avoiding plagiarism; 3) follow the guidelines laid out in the section on “Acknowledgment of data and internal discussions in QUAREP-LiMi working groups” of this CoC; and 4) operate under the general framework of operation as established in the by-laws as the highest governing document.

Transparency & Accountability

Members and other contributors 1) ensure that all contributions and decisions are transparent; 2) clearly document methods, discussions, and results; 3) fairly recognize contributions and foster accountability in collaborative efforts; and 4) communicate inclusively, addressing the widest range of relevant participants, typically the entire working group.

Respectful Communication and Ethical Behavior

Members and other contributors 1) engage with others in a respectful, inclusive, and professional manner; 2) value differences in expertise, background, and opinion as they foster collaboration and lead to more robust outcomes; 3) promote a welcoming atmosphere for participants from various backgrounds, skill levels, and regions; 4) support equitable participation and make room for all voices to be heard; 5) acknowledge that the legal and statutory framework under which contribution by members can be made may vary based on employment status and organizational belonging; 6) declare potential conflicts of interests as they may arise during our work; and 7) declare all affiliations correctly and fully.

Constructive Feedback

Members and other contributors offer constructive, objective feedback during discussions and peer reviews. Critique should focus on improving methodologies and achieving better results, without personal criticism.

Efficient Online Collaboration

Members and other contributors keep online meetings focused and efficient; are punctual and prepared; and ensure that tools and platforms used for collaboration are accessible to all members.

General Expectations & Conflict Resolution

All contributions shall be given in good faith to further the objectives related to quantitative and reproducible light microscopy. No harassment, discrimination, or inappropriate behavior shall be tolerated, and moderators commit to swift action, utilizing as needed the pathways for conflict resolution as defined in the consortium's by-laws.

Authorship and Acknowledgment of Data and Internal Discussions

Reasoning

The aim of QUAREP-LiMi is to bring together Subject Matter Experts (SME or Experts) with expert users in working groups (WG) to drive the development of protocols, best practices, tools and other work products that facilitate quality assessment and reproducibility in light microscopy. All such work products resulting out of work within the consortium need to be sanctioned prior to public release or publication by either the Steering Committee or the Editorial Review Board as described in the by-laws.

Acknowledging internal WG discussions properly is an essential aspect of fostering collaboration, recognizing contributions, and maintaining a positive work environment in the WG. Similarly, work of members of the consortium that they do outside the consortium might overlap with activities within QUAREP-LiMi. Hence, we aim to provide guidance on how to navigate such situations.

SME, Experts and/or expert users likely work on scientific/commercial projects, or in the framework of specific externally funded projects and therefore generating IP associated with institutions or funders that are overlapping or are closely linked/related to the work that is carried out in WGs. Potential conflicts can arise from the fact that it is necessary or a declared goal to publish/commercialize results from such projects as well as from different statutory and legal restraints applicable to different contributors.

The following guidelines are meant to provide a general framework around this topic, help mitigate conflicts, maintain a positive and supportive work culture within the work groups and encourage open communication.

Authorship

Explicit guidance on authorship is given in the Best-Practices document of QUAREP-LiMi that is accessible to all members on the consortium's file sharing infrastructure. It is expected that all kinds of contributions to work products get acknowledged. While academic authorship rules and usage of contributor ontologies underlay our general approach to authorship, it is explicitly acknowledged that many work products might not be peer-reviewed journal

publications and might demand adaptations to authorship rules. Working groups must decide on authorship implementations and indicate authorship within the endorsement process. Members are asked to advocate for themselves, including becoming authors, and to utilize the pathways for conflict resolution as defined in the consortium's by-laws.

Work Products

Work products can be but are not limited to protocols, scripts, software, analysis workflows and other tools or products. Work products that have been developed in working groups and have been published (e.g. via protocols.io) are considered scientific publications and must be treated as such. The use of such work products or part of them is highly encouraged but must be acknowledged with a citation.

Tools that have been developed in working groups and are not published yet or have ongoing discussions beyond a published tool are considered as “personal communication”. For instance, discussions about a next version of a protocol are not “published” through virtue of the original or latest version of the protocol that is currently released. Any use of a tool or part of it must be acknowledged by mentioning QUAREP-LiMi and the respective working group and must be cleared before becoming publicly accessible.

Working Group Data and Other Shared Information

Any data – for example, but not limited to image data, measurements, outputs from software that is being developed – that is provided/collected by a working group is considered confidential unless the opposite is stated explicitly by the data provider. Similarly, confidentiality may be declared by a contributor relating to other contributions, for instance projects still in development at the contributor’s place of work, white papers or other written documents or orally contributed facts.

- a. Data considered confidential must not be shared or used outside the QUAREP-LiMi community.
- b. Non-confidential data may be shared and used outside the QUAREP-LiMi community. In that case, it is mandatory to mention the data provider, QUAREP-LiMi and the respective working group.
- c. It is the responsibility of the party interested in sharing to obtain permission to do so if either confidentiality was declared or the status of confidentiality is not clear. This obligation supersedes but does not resolve the obligation of adequate acknowledgment.

Meeting Recordings

Working group meetings are recorded and made available to the QUAREP-LiMi community. Therefore, any information or content provided in internal working group discussions can be openly shared with QUAREP-LiMi members. Any

information provided in working groups or its internal discussion may only be used outside the QUAREP community with the explicit consent of the working group.

Overlap with Outside Work of Members

QUAREP-LiMi invites and encourages the discussion of ongoing work of members and SMEs within WGs. If such original work, primarily performed outside of the QUAREP-LiMi context, is shared within a WG the owners of such work maintain their full rights and control of such work. QUAREP-LiMi asks that owners do carefully consider if they receive ideas, contributions, critique or review from the WG(s) that justifies acknowledgment in their work in the future.

Collaboration between WG members can originate within the WG but take place in the primary work of the members outside of QUAREP-LiMi. In such cases QUAREP-LiMi asks for general acknowledgment of the WG and the consortium.